
DyMoN Proof of Concept Demonstrations

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Administrative Information

Basic information on the DyMoN project and the present deliverable:

Project title	Dynamic Mobility Nudge: Shaping sustainable urban mobility behaviour with real-time, user generated and public open data
Project coordinator	Salzburg Research Forschungsgesellschaft mbH (SRFG), Salzburg, Austria; project coordinator: Dr. Claudia Luger-Bazinger
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Purpose of the document

The document aims to outline activities, process and responsibility under WP4 of the DyMoN project. It serves as guidelines for policy recommendations and briefing on appropriate digital nudging for sustainable urban mobility.

Executive Summary

The Proof of Concept Demonstrations Package (WP4) supports the DyMoN project in achieving its objectives in terms of promoting sustainable urban mobility behaviour through digital nudging. The document describes the proof of concept activities that were carried out in Salzburg, Austria, and in Uppsala, Sweden. In Salzburg, the integrative capability of the situation-aware nudges was demonstrated by using it with a mobile application to investigate the effects of digital nudges on sustainable mobility behaviours, specifically, commuting. In Uppsala, an international hackathon was organised with the aim of finding solutions for sustainable development and enabling safe, clean and affordable sustainable mobility, using digital nudging as a tool for effective changes.

1 Introduction

The Proof-of-Concept Demonstrations within the DyMoN project were as follows:

- proof of concept of the **behavioural aspects of situation-aware nudging** for investigating the **effects** on urban sustainable mobility of citizens in Salzburg,
- proof of concept of the **flexibility of the concept of situation-aware nudging** to integrate new research prototypes developed in a transnational hackathon.

Consequently, we designed two different approaches for the proof of concept. At the first stage, integration with an existing mobile application in Salzburg, the use of digital nudges, and the documentation of the effects on sustainable mobility behaviour of citizens were realized. Subsequently, in Uppsala a hackathon was organised, involving teams from different countries in the development of ideas, scaling of the DyMoN idea and prototyping mobility behaviour apps that could be suitable for many cities.

The WP4 activities relate to other project work: it provides the data for the evaluation of the functionality of the DyMoN data hub and nudge ontology (WP3), the effect of the nudging repository on sustainable mobility choices (WP2), and the overall evaluation of the demonstration results (WP5).

2 Proof of Concept in Salzburg, Austria

2.1 Location and target group

The DyMoN proof of concept took place in a neighborhood in Salzburg, called Science City Itzling.¹ The activity was coordinated and led by Salzburg Research and carried out in cooperation with University of Salzburg (Department of Geoinformatics) and Trafficon.

Employees of companies located at Science City Itzling took part in the sustainable mobility campaign “Science City Aktiv Mobil”. The target group were people who are currently often using their car to get to work, but who could use more sustainable, active modes of transport (walking, bicycling) or public transport. Therefore, we chose the focus of commuting behaviour, although the general idea of DyMoN could also be transferred to mobility during weekends or outside of work.

The project team reached out to several companies, which distributed information about the campaign to their employees to recruit participants for the field test. In addition, posters were put up around the Science City Salzburg with a link for the campaign registration page (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Poster with information about the campaign “Science City Aktiv Mobil”.

For the registration, a welcome page was set up on the project website, which offered all the necessary information and details for participants to join the field test and served as first contact point with companies that were interested in taking part (see Figure 2).

¹ <https://www.techno-z.at/en/location-and-service/university-and-research/>

Figure 2: Screenshots of the registration page (<https://dymon.eu/science-city-aktiv-mobil-anmeldung/>).

2.2. Supporting events

Several activities accompanied the campaign to provide a meaningful setting for the participants and to develop a sense of community which are important for the success of such campaigns (Luger-Bazinger & Hornung-Prähauser, 2021).

On 23 March 2023 the campaign started with a kick-off event, led by project coordinator Dr. Claudia Luger-Bazinger and David Leistner, in which people interested to participate in the field test were informed about the campaign, and received an onboarding, followed by a lunch for networking (see Figure 3). On that occasion a bicycle repair station was provided.

Figure 3: The kick-off event with a short presentation and networking opportunity.

On 20 April 2023, Dr. Birgit Böhm from the Technical University Munich offered a talk on how physical activity in everyday life is necessary for the cardiovascular system and overall well-being, and how a change from car use to sustainable forms of commuting can support a healthy lifestyle (see Figure 4).

Figure 4: Talk by Dr. Birgit Böhm during the campaign.

To ensure continuous engagement, incentives and prizes were used, for example vouchers for filling out the online surveys. One incentive was a community picnic, that was held if the participants reached a certain number of points during the campaign (see Figure 5). The picnic was held on 1 June 2023 and marked the end of the proof of concept campaign.

Figure 5: Community picnic with raffle winners and members of the project team.

2.3 Campaign app, participation and procedure

In the campaign, Pandocs², an Austrian app, was used to interact with the DyMoN system and receive nudge messages. Pandocs has been developed for holistic workplace health promotion (e.g., fitness, mental wellbeing, nutrition). The advantage of not using an app specifically for mobility behaviour is that the Pandocs app offers more content for a broader audience than an app that is, for example, already geared towards bicycling.

On the campaign registration page (see Figure 2) the participants received a detailed description on how to download the app and connect their individual user account with the group “Science City Aktiv Mobil”. After doing this, the participants could see on their smartphone the content that was prepared for the campaign and receive digital nudges.

In the Pandocs app, a new category for active mobility was introduced for the campaign (see Figure 6):

Figure 6: Screenshots of campaign content as seen by the users of the Pandocs app.

² <https://www.pandocs.com/en/>

Here, the participants could collect gamified points for sustainable commutes to and from work, receive information about the DyMoN dashboard and links to online surveys (see below). Participants could decide for which kind of sustainable mobility mode they wanted to receive motivational nudges and could switch between modes if needed. The content of the nudge messages was adjusted automatically.

Around 60 participants took part and received digital nudges for using sustainable mobility options in the form of push notifications via the app (see below) that could be triggered by situational data such as weather or traffic conditions. A number of digital nudges from the nudging repository were tested; see D2.2a “Nudging Repository” (DyMoN 2023a/b), and for the technical implementation, D3.1 “DyMoN data hub” (DyMoN 2023c) and Loidl et al. (2023). For the demonstration the nudges were translated into German and shortened to fit the requirements of the Pandocs app (for examples see Figure 7 and the Appendix).

Figure 7: Example of nudges sent as notifications to Pandocs app users.

The participants received two nudges per day, one in the morning, one in the evening, except on Saturday and Sunday. On Sunday, a notification was only sent in the evening. Nudges were sent from 23 March to 23 May 2023.

The proof of concept demonstrations involved two groups of participants. Participants in the intervention group received situation-aware nudges, which took into account situational factors such as weather or traffic conditions. The control group received only generic nudges with no situational component (see also D5.1 “Project Evaluation and Impact Plan”, DyMoN 2023d).

To visualize the situational components that influenced nudges, a dashboard was provided by the project partner Trafficon (see Figure 8). The dashboard was displayed at screens in the buildings in the Science City Itzling, as well as online on a designated website.

Figure 8: Screenshot of the dashboard provided by Trafficon.

In the Pandocs app group “Science City Aktiv Mobil”, we provided “challenges” that only campaign participants could see. Here the participants could confirm that they commuted to work with sustainable mobility modes by finishing the associated challenge (“Radl-Tag” for bike, “Gut zu Fuß” for walking and “Bus und Bahn” for public transport). For this they received “Lebenspunkte” (life points) from the gamification system of Pandocs.

Over the course of the campaign, participants were asked to fill out two online surveys, one at the beginning and one at the end of the campaign. These surveys were also designed as “challenges” for which participants could get points after finishing a survey, similar to the mobility challenges. Accessing information about the Dashboard was also presented as a challenge. In addition, participants could answer a short quiz about the dashboard to gain some extra points.

2.4 Summary and lessons learned

The Living Lab approach used for this campaign provided a way to test the functionality of the situation-aware nudging in a real-life demonstration and to gather feedback by users. The full analysis of results can be found in D5.2 “Evaluation of pilot demonstrations”, but our first analysis showed that nudges containing health information, climate information and inspiration were voted as the most motivating. Regarding the different parts of the campaign, events were the most motivating aspect, closely followed by the nudges and the gamification elements.

The importance attributed to the events show that digital nudging should be embedded in a social setting. Campaigns in a neighborhood or within a company require information events, onboarding and guidance of participants, and can support a sense of community. Events give structure to a campaign and can create a deeper commitment.

One of the biggest challenges is to find, motivate and retain participants. A strong motivator of our campaign seemed to be the gamification aspects of the Pandocs app in combination with the community goal of reaching 25,000 points together. The collected points proved to be a conversation starter and a way for our participants to connect at the campaign events. Additionally, incentives like the community picnic at 25,000 points and the vouchers for completing the surveys seemed to contribute to keeping participants motivated.

Despite events and incentives, it requires considerable effort to reach and retain the desired target group for such a campaign. A promising alternative approach could be to run campaigns with large companies that are interested in promoting sustainable mobility to their employees.

The number of nudges sent should be considered thoroughly. Since people already get a lot of notifications on their smartphone, for some the additional campaign nudges seemed more bothersome than motivational. Two nudges, one in the morning and one in the evening, seemed to be a good solution, however, even this was too much for some of the participants. It appears that the more nudges can be personalized the more relevant they are perceived.

2.5 Good practices for using digital nudges for sustainable mobility

Reaching your target group: The focus and topic of the campaign app is important for reaching the right audience. If the app is already geared towards sustainability, this might be “preaching to the choir”, hence reaching only people who already have sustainable mobility habits.

- **Tip:** Sustainable, active mobility can be combined with different topics, such as fitness, health or even frugal living.

More is not always better: Sending too many push notifications can overwhelm users. The number and timing of the notifications should be planned so that the campaign does not appear as aggressive.

- **Tip:** Consider that less is more when nudging. In our experience, two push notifications per day are the absolute maximum. Furthermore, the more personalized the nudge messages are, the more relevant they will be perceived.

Testing before getting started: Not properly integrating the various data needed to generate useful situation-aware nudges will be detrimental to your efforts.

- **Tip:** We recommend a test run for at least two weeks with a friendly user group that gives detailed feedback.

Social context is important: Digital nudging needs social context and sufficient time for onboarding participants and community-building.

- **Tip:** We used a mobility campaign with multiple events such as talks and community lunches to onboard people and in addition to written instructions help them use the app.

Incentives work: Incentives are helpful in attracting participants and keeping them engaged. Incentives can take the form of a small prize for each individual participant after a certain goal was reached or a raffle for a bigger prize.

- **Tip:** Community can also be fostered with incentives (e.g. a group picnic). Special events with unique experiences are usually more appreciated and are more sustainable than giving away many presents to individual participants.

One size does not fit all: Not tailoring nudges to diverse audiences, mobility modes and situations can lead to losing target groups or subgroups (e.g. people taking care of elderly or children).

- **Tip:** Consider a wide spectrum of people with different lifestyles, opportunities and capabilities. By doing so, their diverse needs can be better supported. It is often the group left out who need support the most.

Quality in, quality out: Investment in rich and sound data will pay off in the quality of the service that builds upon the data.

- **Tip:** In situation-aware nudging the better the data is, and the more data can be integrated, the better the quality of the nudging will be.

3 Proof of Concept in Uppsala, Sweden

3.1 Hackathon event

In Uppsala, Sweden, an international hackathon served as the proof of concept. The event was organised with the goal of discovering solutions for sustainable development and advancing secure and environmentally friendly transportation. Nudging was employed as a tool to instigate changes, communicate effectively, and scale the DyMoN concept. The participating “hackers”, were tasked with devising methods to disseminate nudges beyond those implemented in Salzburg, enhancing the overall scope of the framework.

The “Sustainable Mobility Hackathon & Meet UP” (SUMMUP) took place on 11-12 May 2023, adopting a hybrid format that included both in-person participation at the Green Innovation Park in Uppsala and virtual attendance through platforms such as Zoom, YouTube, and other online streaming channels (Figure 9). Participants had the opportunity to watch the event in real time and ask questions on YouTube or via the online community on Slack.

Figure 9: Finalists of the “Sustainable Mobility Hackathon & Meet UP” present their ideas.

The Sustainability InnoCenter (Uppsala, Sweden) took charge of coordinating this event. In addition to the core partners of the DyMoN project, various local partners from Swedish cities, including key players in their innovation systems, actively participated in the initiative. Among these collaborators were Uppsala University, Uppsala Innovation Centre, the county of Uppsala, Uppsala municipality, Green Innovation Park, Gävle municipality, Gävle Innovation Hub, DrivHuset, Världklass Uppsala, Ericsson, Nudgd (a digital service provider), and numerous others (Figure 10 for details).

Figure 10: Partners of the “Sustainable Mobility Hackathon & Meet UP”.

Attendance at the event was open to individuals, but engagement in the hackathon necessitated the formation or joining of a team, with solo entries not allowed. Organizers actively facilitated the team formation process, leading to the creation of 11 teams. Overall, 128 individuals enthusiastically took part in the hackathon.

The event saw participation from a total of 200 individuals, comprising jury members, partners, and enthusiasts interested in the mobility theme. Moreover, the Hackathon's website drew approximately 7,000 unique visitors.

The proof of concept hackathon aimed to engage a diverse range of participants interested in generating ideas and solutions for the presented challenges. This inclusive group included sustainability experts, city planners, regional and municipal employees, representatives from transport companies, IT professionals, advocates from cycling promotion organizations, as well as researchers and students from various disciplines. Notably, a significant portion of the participants were young individuals, symbolizing a potent force for driving future changes (Figure 11).

Figure 11: Young participants of the “Sustainable Mobility Hackathon & Meet UP”.

The event adopted a hybrid format, enabling individuals from anywhere in Uppsala or beyond to participate. The sustainability hackathon welcomed participants free of charge. For those attending in person and committing to the full two-day (48-hour) experience, complimentary breakfast, lunch, and dinner were provided (Figure 12).

Figure 12: Hackathon participants continued to solve challenges even during breaks.

To foster and maintain high levels of engagement, various incentives and prizes were offered to motivate teams, tailored to enhance their enthusiasm and dedication towards further developing the ideas created during the hackathon. These incentives were designed not only to recognize their efforts but also to catalyze the continued development of their projects.

The concept of the hackathon included organizing the event in a way that is enjoyable and relaxed for its participants. Such events are a great opportunity for networking with people who share common interests – in this case, sustainability issues and using behavioural change techniques to promote sustainable transport (see Figure 13).

Figure 13: Representatives of the hackathon case owners.

The hackathon process was divided into 3 phases:

1. Preparatory activities (planning, negotiations with partners, communication campaign, invitations, booking speakers, registration, arranging venues and catering).
2. Two-day hackathon (11-12 May 2023).
3. Post hackathon activities (including summary meetings with the participating actors who had presented challenges for the local partners to solve) (see Figure 14).

Figure 14: Hackathon timeline.

The first phase began more than eight months in advance of the main event, starting in October 2022. During the initial weeks, various tasks were undertaken, including the development of the hackathon programme, negotiations with key local partners, coordination of actions with project partners, selection of the event venue, and identification of primary subcontractors (see Figure 15).

Figure 15: A meeting of the Sustainability InnoCenter team with the city of Gävle and Gävle Innovation Arena (Gävle, 19 April 2023).

In February 2023, Sustainability InnoCenter, responsible for this part of the project, initiated a large and broad communication campaign. For the campaign and subsequent activities an official hackathon [website](#) was launched (see Figure 16). The website contained all the necessary information, including the DyMoN project description, the hackathon programme, answers to frequently asked questions, details about participating in the hackathon, etc. The site attracted approximately 7,000 unique visitors during the preparation and event period.

Figure 16: Hackathon website homepage (screenshot).

Digital posters were created and a special [video](#) with information about the hackathon. These were posted on all informational channels of Sustainability InnoCenter ([website](#), [Facebook](#), [LinkedIn](#)) and the [DyMoN](#) project website (see Figure 17).

Figure 17: Promotional video of the hackathon (screenshot).

Information about the hackathon the DyMoN project was also published on websites and social media and included in newsletters of the partners. The event was extensively promoted by Swedish universities targeting both students and faculty (Uppsala University, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, the Royal Institute of Technology in Stockholm, Malmö University, Dalarna and Gävle Universities, etc.), as well as companies (UL, Chromia, Ericsson, UIC, Drivhuset), innovation hubs and startup centers (Uppsala Innovative Center, Green Innovation Park, Science Park Gotland, Chromia Innovation Lab, Gävle Innovation Hub, etc.) and Swedish municipalities (Uppsala, Gävle, Kalmar, Malmö, Dalarna, and Umeå) (see Figures 18 and 19).

Figure 18: Hackathon information on the Uppsala commune website (screenshot).

Figure 19: Hackathon information on the University of Gävle LinkedIn page (screenshot).

On 3 March 2023, the [kick-off event](#) took place at Green Innovation Park in Uppsala. Some 40 attendees participated in the session, receiving an introduction to the project and engaging in discussions on the power of open innovation for sustainable growth and impact. Harris Stamatopoulos, director of Sustainability InnoCenter, gave some examples of creative solutions generated by hackathons he had initiated, led and participated in over the last years. Among the participants were several representatives of startups in Uppsala.

During the preparation period, the Sustainability InnoCenter team held a series of meetings with representatives of the cities of Uppsala and Gävle, Gävle Innovation Arena and other stakeholders. These meetings focused on the development and coordination of the hackathon challenges. This was done to ensure that the results of the hackathon could be useful and implemented in the nearest future.

In early March 2023, the registration page for the two-day hackathon was implemented on the event website and the registration process started.

3.2 Hackathon challenges

To participate in the hackathon, the teams formed by the registered participants had to select and solve one of three challenges that had been developed in close cooperation with the Uppsala Municipality, the Uppsala University, and the Gävle Municipality, respectively (see Figure 20).

Figure 20: The posters with the titles of the hackathon challenges.

1. **“Uppsala municipality challenge”**. Increasing the proportion of people walking and cycling in Uppsala is an important sustainability goal of the municipality. Having more pedestrians and cyclists in Uppsala leads to a reduced load on public transport, decreased congestion, and fewer emissions of greenhouse gasses and particles. Additionally, having more pedestrians and cyclists also contributes to fewer cars on the road, which in turn reduces the risk of accidents. The shared ambition of the municipalities in Sweden is that no one should die or be seriously injured in traffic.

The Uppsala municipality has a mobility pool and a digital booking platform that employees are free to use, including cars, bikes and other modes of transport. However, the digital platform and thus the mobility pool it is not used as much as the municipality would like. The goal of the hackathon challenge was to increase the effectiveness of the mobility pool by improving the platform (e.g., streamline the vehicle reservation process), increase the number of users, and use behaviour change techniques to promote sustainable transport.

2. **“Nudgd challenge”**. The second challenge revolved around working with the Smart Nudges Platform, developed by [Nudgd](#), which employs personalized and smart nudges to promote behaviour changes. The Nudging Sweden network is Scandinavia’s largest community for anyone who would like to learn more about nudging. It consists of more than 3,200 professionals working in 40 different organisations and businesses. Members have access to exclusive master classes, networking as well as digital meetups to exchange best practices and organize collaborations.

The Smart Nudges Platform is available to use either as stand-alone web app for mobile devices and computers or integrated via an API in third-party applications. Some examples of applications include native apps (MaaS, public transport planning, etc.), intranets for employees or tenants, extranets/my pages, and more.

The task was to find creative, accessible, and innovative ways to engage car users in a non-intrusive manner with sustainability issues, which could be adapted and implemented for various stakeholders, including companies/workplaces, municipalities, public transport providers, real estate companies or others.

3. “Gävle city challenge”. Gävle regularly ranks as one of Sweden’s most sustainable cities and has high ambitions to grow and transform in the coming years. The municipality recently passed 100,000 inhabitants and like Uppsala, the municipality has struck an agreement with the government to develop new sustainable city districts, and a modern logistics park in exchange for new rail infrastructure connecting to the East Coast Line. Until 2030, to achieve climate neutrality, the city wants to drastically transform transportation within the city by doubling the biking share of transport, doubling the share of public transport, and moving heavy transport out of the inner city.

The Gävle challenge focused on promoting sustainable transportation related to a comprehensive initiative of the Gävle municipality called “Year-Round Cyclists”. The initiative includes the development of a technical application accompanied by a reward system to encourage users to embrace sustainable transportation modes. Additionally, it will incorporate an information campaign aimed at educating users about the advantages of sustainable transportation and provide guidance on planning and optimizing sustainable transportation routes. The goal of this challenge was to identify potential challenges that the Gävle municipality might encounter when implementing the platform of the initiative and prioritize three of these challenges. Finally, participants were tasked with proposing the best solutions for the top-priority challenge.

The teams’ selection of the proposed challenges was distributed as follows (see Figure 21):

Figure 21: The distribution of teams according to their chosen challenges (result from SurveyMonkey platform).

Throughout the hackathon, participants actively interacted with representatives of the Uppsala and Gävle municipalities, seeking information about the presented challenges, insights into the inner workings of the municipalities, and daily life in the respective communities. The municipality experts showed genuine enthusiasm in responding to the questions, driven by their interest in obtaining practical solutions from the “hackers”. In turn, the “hackers” appreciated the opportunity to interact directly with the challenge owners, as it provided valuable insights that could not be obtained through online research alone. Representatives of

the Uppsala and Gävle municipalities and Uppsala University were also part of the jury that decided on the winners of the hackathon (see Figure 22).

Figure 22: Hackathon jury members listening to the presentation of one of the teams.

The hybrid format of the hackathon enabled some of the presenters who could not physically come to the event to participate and present their solutions online; the presentations were shown on a large screen in the conference room.

3.3 Key ideas from the winners

The new solutions obtained during the two-day hackathon offered a valuable opportunity to enhance our project's effectiveness and innovation, particularly in recognizing the important role of nudges. The most interesting and unconventional solutions were presented by three teams, each working on a different challenge. These teams the winners of the hackathon: SustainUT (case title: "Uppsala booking platform"), NudgeExperience ("How to nudge outside the app"), and Astra Tech ("Nudging inside the public transportation company UL app").

SustainUT

The SustainUT solution of the team that took first place (see Figure 23) displays various travel options in a highly graphic and compelling way. SustainUT highlights the potential for incorporating nudging into various systems, such as the mobility pool booking system of the Uppsala municipality. Currently, the system's default option is cars. However, as the team demonstrated, it could be changed to favor alternative modes of transportation.

The solution developed during the hackathon was to build an **intelligent vehicle management platform** that includes personalised recommendations and optimised resource utilisation, **substituting unsustainable practices** with **responsible asset usage** based on tracked user data (see Figure 24). Based on the insights obtained from the collected data, the solution's functions aim to customise, maximise, discourage, supplement, and learn.

Figure 23. SustainUT team, the hackathon's winner, during the award ceremony.

In their ideas for the solution, SustainUT concentrated on the following areas:

- Behaviour change by nudging
- Integration of public transport
- Incentivisation using blockchain
- Personalisation using artificial intelligence methods.

In particular, for behaviour change and nudging, their suggestions were as follows:

- Promote sustainable alternatives
- Employ nudging techniques to discourage unsustainable choices by making unsustainable options less attractive and complicating their selection
- Persuade employees to opt for sustainable modes of transport

Addressing the challenges of sustainable travel behaviour, the “hackers” focused on the following:

- Providing personalised recommendations and optimising resource utilisation through artificial intelligence methods
- Influencing employees travel choices.
- Tailoring integrated modes of transport to individual preferences
- Promoting the adoption of sustainable options
- Integrating with Google Maps and UL System (UL is the main provider of public transport services in Uppsala).

All measures aim to reduce car usage, traffic congestion, and greenhouse gas emissions.

Figure 24. Illustration of the SustainUT app that includes personalised recommendations and optimised resource utilisation (screenshot from the presentation of the SustainUT team).

The SustainUT team also provided their examples of nudges:

- Example 1: “Nudging will work by tracking how frequently users orient towards unsustainable solutions, and gently remind them of that fact during their next unsustainable choice selection”.
- Example 2: “Users will receive nudges about team activities. If bike usage has been high but the user is lagging behind the norm, even if they are capable, the prompts will intuitively suggest making more sustainable choices”.

Moreover, they pointed out the need to avoid excessive notifications, punishments, and exclusions. According to the hackathon participants, notifications should only be sent during interactions, and praise should be based on effort and ability.

The SustainUT team also presented potential outcomes and impacts from the use of the nudges:

- **A scalable and familiar app** that enables testing of new features and solutions in more flexible ways. The core functionality should be familiar to the user.
- **Emphasis on responsibility of the entire community**, recognizing that habits start at home, but that we all need to make the shift to create a more sustainable society.
- **A commitment to realistic and effective solutions**, based on data on demographic and employee profiles as well as organisational needs and planning.
- **The value of connection and opportunity**. Opportunities for collaborative solutions in research and practice, e.g., promoting carpooling as a service.

The team’s graphics illustrated what different options mean in terms of societal, environmental, and economic sustainability (see Figure 25).

Figure 26: Examples of the posters proposed by the NudgeExperience team.

2. **Developing new immersive experiences using visually attractive physical artifacts**, such as a projector installation on bike or pedestrian routes to display measures, activities and benefits (e.g., cinnamon buns), or an image illustrating how many bikes can occupy the space of a car on the road (see Figure 27).

Figure 27: Examples of visually attractive physical artifacts proposed by the NudgeExperience team.

3. **Implementing elements of surprise and nudging prompts**: The team proposed installing movement sensors on the bike path that would illuminate the nearest lamp. The brightness would increase with higher bike frequency and fade as bike traffic decreases. This feature would activate only for bikes and pedestrians, not cars (see Figure 28). Additionally, they suggested providing users with new bike routes: the Scenic Route and the Safe Route.

Figure 28: Image of movement sensors on the bike path, presented by the NudgeExperience team.

4. **Promoting community cohesion through social comparison and nurturing a sense of community.** This could be achieved through organizing cycling competitions between municipalities and a supporting information platform. The platform presents the accumulated miles for each municipality on a board and also allows sharing other valuable community information. Encouraging participation could be achieved by establishing a mileage leaderboard on Resvanal and highlighting the importance of bike customisation (see Figure 29).

Figure 29. Example of an information board that presents the accumulated miles for Uppsala (screenshot from the NudgeExperience team presentation).

Astra Tech

The team of the third winner, Astra Tech, focused their solution on enhancing Uppsala transportation with new functionalities and a reward system in the already existing app of UL, which is the main provider of public transport services in Uppsala (see Figure 30). The team combined different IT components that made their solution highly functional and trustworthy. They used a credit system as a nudging method, allowing users of the app to earn credits for products they buy in different stores. Blockchain technology was an important part of the solution. By identifying the user via blockchain technology, they made it more trustworthy and assured that the right user gets the right credit.

Figure 30. New functionalities and reward system for UL (screenshot from the presentation of the Astra Tech team).

Some benefits and impacts proposed by the Astra Tech team are:

- Unified platform for public transport, e-bikes and e-scooters
- Tokens collected by users can be used as rewards (e.g. discounts, promos), serving as a positive nudge
- The Token-Reward Collection System is based on a sustainable transport hierarchy (see Figure 31)
- The Referral Networking System can reward the users

Figure 31. Illustration of the concept of the sustainable transport hierarchy by the Astra Tech team.

The team also proposed collaborate with other renowned organisations and companies to enhance the effect of the application. The concept was to allow users to exchange accumulated credits in various stores, pharmacies, and similar places for goods (see Figure 32).

Figure 32. Example of potential collaboration between UL and other organisations and companies proposed by the Astra Tech team.

The team concluded that the UL application should become a unified platform for an improved transportation–reward–wellness nexus, which could significantly increase UL users. At the same time, they stressed the need for market stimulation in Uppsala. The team also noted that the UL app should support users of all ages, promote inclusivity & diversity, and track the user's environmental footprint.

3.4. Summary and lessons learned

The hackathon was followed by a series of results presentations and meetings with the DyMoN consortium (May 2023), representatives from the Uppsala and Gävle communes, regional innovation stakeholders (see Figure 33). It was agreed to implement useful outcomes of the hackathon and continue the pursuit of new initiatives. Specifically, commune representatives are considering implementing the ideas developed during the Hackathon into their traffic departments and integrating nudges into their everyday practices.

Figure 33: Post-hackathon meeting of Sustainability InnoCenter staff, hackathon winners and representatives of Uppsala commune at the Innovation Lab of Uppsala city.

We summarize some lessons learned from the hackathon and post-hackathon process that the project consortium learned within the proof of concept in Uppsala:

- **Use nudges in existing applications.** Get the most out of the existing pool of users. Building a new user base takes time. An already engaged population or a community in an already existing service might already be the best target audience to start with.
- **Collaborate with other organisations and companies when implementing nudge campaigns to reach a larger audience.** Attracting individual citizens as users requires much time and resources. Seeking collaborations with other organisations and companies can be more efficient for attracting many users.
- **To engage individuals who are resistant to nudging, it is essential to develop more extensive and innovative campaigns.** This requires a more comprehensive approach to understanding resistant people, an appropriate toolbox, and a diverse mix of media channels.
- **The set of nudges (i.e., the DyMoN nudging repository) is central to promoting behaviour change.** The nudges need to be distributed through different channels to the target groups.
- **Taking a systemic perspective to disseminate nudges requires understanding the mix of systems in which the user is engaged.** These systems can be multifaceted, including, for example, intranets, calendars, and platforms for various resources.
- **Incorporating gamification into the nudge implementation across platforms and apps encourages greater participation,** transforming sustainability into an enjoyable pursuit rather than a mandatory duty.
- Reaching out to various subpopulations is essential, but it is widely understood that **the younger population**, which is using more digital tools, **tends to be the most receptive to digital nudging.**
- **Learning about the habits of the users is key to nudging.** The more information we have about users, the more efficient nudging campaigns will be.
- **The application of artificial intelligence on data from different applications could allow learning more about user behaviours and their responses to nudging.** If AI can assist in understanding what works and what does not it could lead to increased efficiency in nudging overall.
- **A nudging system with incentives such as credit earnings could be an interesting solution.** Using the preferred means of sustainable transport could be rewarded with credits (e.g., blockchain tokens) which can be exchanged for coupons, tickets or discounts from business partners in the region.
- **Complement nudging through digital channels with promotional events in collaboration with NGOs, public and private organisations.** Opinion leaders and ambassadors of renowned organisations can help make the case for more use of behaviour change methods to promote using sustainable transport modes such as active mobility (walk, bike) and public transport.
- **Encourage events that enhance social bonding, and networking that makes showcase behaviour change.** The influence of a group can have as much effect as advertising.

- **Trust is an important factor for success.** Trust building methods, e.g., blockchain for verification in a credit system, can support that the right users are recognized and receive rewards for their sustainable behaviour.
- **Punishment is not nudging.** Imposing fines as a deterrent for unsustainable transportation practices is not merely nudging; it goes beyond gentle encouragement and aims to induce behavioral change through punitive measures.

4 Conclusion

In this document, we have reported the work under the DyMoN project's Proof of Concept Demonstrations Package (WP4). Within the proof of concept, two main activities were realized in Salzburg, Austria, and Uppsala, Sweden, which were accompanied by a dozen supporting events. These activities have led to significant improvement in understanding the different aspects of digital nudging for sustainable urban mobility.

In Salzburg, the proof of concept illustrated the integration of situation-aware nudges within a mobile application, emphasizing the impact of digital nudges on fostering sustainable commuting behaviour. The local campaign, "Science City Aktiv Mobil", specifically targeted individuals who predominantly used cars for their daily transportation but had the potential to transition to more sustainable alternatives. Employing a Living Lab approach, the campaign tested the functionality of situation-aware nudging in a real-life demonstration and collected feedback from participants.

The results revealed that the most motivating nudges were those that contained health and climate information, along with inspirational content. Noteworthy, within the campaign's various components, events were the most motivating, closely followed by nudges and gamification elements. Moreover, it was established that the success of a digital nudging campaign depends on various factors, including tailoring the topic to its intended audience, striking the right balance in the frequency and personalization of notifications, conducting thorough testing, creating a social context for engagement, offering effective incentives, addressing diverse audiences and situations, and investing in quality data. These elements help effectively reach and engage the target audience, thereby fostering changes in mobility behaviour in a sustainable manner.

In Uppsala, the proof of concept took the form of an international hackathon, named "Sustainable Mobility Hackathon & Meet UP". This event aimed to generate innovative solutions for sustainable mobility using nudging as a catalyst for behaviour change. Meanwhile, participants worked with methods to distribute nudges beyond the confines of the Salzburg campaign.

The hackathon underscored several key points. It highlighted the value of integrating nudges into existing applications, emphasized the importance of collaborating with other organizations and companies to efficiently engage a broader audience, and stressed the significance of developing innovative campaigns to attract individuals resistant to nudging. It was found that the repository of nudges and their distribution through various channels plays an essential role in behaviour change. Furthermore, gamification across different platforms and apps encouraged active participation and made sustainability more enjoyable. Additionally, it was noted that younger people, well-versed in digital tools, are more receptive to digital nudging.

Also, the important role of the systemic perspective was highlighted for disseminating nudges, the role of artificial intelligence in enhancing nudging efficiency, and the potential for incentive-based systems. Trust-building mechanisms, such as blockchain verification, were recognized as vital factors for success. Complementing digital nudging with promotional events and involving opinion leaders and reputable organizations emerged as effective strategies to encourage the adoption of sustainable transport modes.

In conclusion, the lessons learned from the proof of concept activities provide a foundation for the successful application of digital nudging to promote sustainable urban mobility behaviour. These insights serve as valuable data for evaluating the DyMoN data hub and nudge ontology, as well as for assessing the impact of the nudging repository and the overall results of the demonstrations.

5 References

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6 Appendix

Table 1: List of Nudges used for the campaign (in German).

These nudges are German translations from the DyMoN nudging repository. For more details please see the full nudging repository: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7620003>

Title	Übersetzung
Wusstest du...	dass es einen schönen Fußweg gleich bei dir in der Nähe gibt? Erkunde den doch morgen! 🧡🌲
Morgen ist ein super Tag...	um mit dem Radl zu fahren! Plan doch schon deine Fahrt, damit du pünktlich ankommst und alles dabei hast! 🚲
Morgen ist ein super Tag...	um zu Fuß zur Arbeit zu gehen! Plan doch schon mal, was du dafür brauchst (z.B. Sackerl, um noch einkaufen zu gehen). 🧡
Hast du schon mal überlegt...	Gewand zum Umziehen oder Deo für einen frischen Start im Büro zu lagern? Damit wäre das Radln in die Arbeit viel angenehmer! 🚲
Morgen ist ein super Tag...	um mit den Öffis zur Arbeit zu fahren! Warum planst du nicht jetzt schon deine Fahrt, wann du los musst, was du mitnimmst... 🚆
Wie oft...	möchtest du in der Woche mit dem Radl zur Arbeit fahren? Setz dir doch ein Ziel! 🚲🎯
Möchtest du diese Woche...	nicht zumindest einmal das Auto gegen die Öffis eintauschen? Was wäre dein Ziel? 🚆🎯
Wie wär's...	mit einem Spaziergang zur Arbeit diese Woche? Den ganzen Weg oder zumindest einen Teil davon - was ist dein Ziel? 🧡🎯
Was hält dich davon ab...	mit dem Radl in die Arbeit zu fahren? Was sind für dich die größten Hürden und was würde helfen (z.B. frisches Gewand im Büro)? 🚲
Was hält dich davon ab...	am Wochenende mit dem Radl zu fahren? Was sind für dich die größten Hürden und was würde helfen (z.B. großer Rucksack für Einkäufe)? 🚲
Was hält dich davon ab...	die Öffis für den Weg zur Arbeit zu nutzen? Was sind für dich die größten Hürden und was würde helfen (z.B. ein Buch mitnehmen)? 🚆
Was hält dich davon ab...	zu Fuß zur Arbeit zu gehen? Was sind für dich die größten Hürden und was würde helfen (z.B. beim Heimgehen noch zum Supermarkt)? 🧡
Was hält dich davon ab...	am Wochenende mit den Öffis zu fahren? Was sind für dich die größten Hürden und was würde helfen (z.B. ein Buch mitnehmen)? 🚆
Hast du Kolleg:innen...	die jeden Tag mit den Öffis zur Arbeit fahren? Schnapp sie dir auf einen Kaffee und frag nach Tipps und Unterstützung! 🚆☕
Hast du Kolleg:innen...	die jeden Tag zu Fuß zur Arbeit gehen? Schnapp sie dir auf einen Kaffee und frag nach Tipps und Unterstützung! 🧡☕
Hast du Kolleg:innen...	die jeden Tag mit dem Radl zur Arbeit kommen? Schnapp sie dir auf einen Kaffee und frag nach Tipps und Unterstützung! 🚲☕
Hast du Kolleg:innen...	die gar kein Auto haben? Schnapp sie dir auf einen Kaffee und frag nach ihren Tipps und Unterstützung! ☕😊
Plane doch...	deine Radlfahrt für morgen, damit du mit viel Schwung und sicher ankommst! 🚲
Wusstest du...	dass Sitzen das neue Rauchen ist? Hilf deinem Körper mit mehr Bewegung im Alltag - fahr jeden Tag mit dem Radl! 🚲😊
Wusstest du...	dass Sitzen das neue Rauchen ist? Hilf deinem Körper mit mehr Bewegung im Alltag - geh jeden Tag zu Fuß! 🧡😊
Tägliche Bewegung kann dir helfen...	fit zu bleiben! Die tägliche Radlfahrt hilft! 🚲
Tägliche Bewegung kann dir helfen...	fit zu bleiben! Der tägliche Fußweg hilft! 🧡

Du kannst jeden Tag eine Menge CO2 sparen...	wenn du mit dem Radl statt mit dem Auto fährst! 🚲🌳
Du kannst jeden Tag eine Menge CO2 sparen...	wenn du zu Fuß gehst, statt mit dem Auto zu fahren! 🌳👣
Du kannst jeden Tag eine Menge CO2 sparen...	wenn du die Öffis nutzt statt des Autos! 🌳🚌
Wusstest du...	dass häufige Folgen von zu viel Sitzen Rückenprobleme, Gewichtszunahme und sogar Ängste und Depressionen sind? Nutz im Alltag doch lieber das Radl! 🚲
Wusstest du...	dass häufige Folgen von zu viel Sitzen Rückenprobleme, Gewichtszunahme und sogar Ängste und Depressionen sind? Geh doch im Alltag mehr zu Fuß! 👣😊
Wusstest du...	dass zu viele Autofahrten zu Umweltverschmutzung, Verkehrschaos und Klimaerwärmung führen? 😞 Leiste deinen Beitrag und fahr mit dem Radl! 🚲
Wusstest du...	dass zu viele Autofahrten zu Umweltverschmutzung, Verkehrschaos und Klimaerwärmung führen? 😞 Leiste deinen Beitrag und geh zu Fuß! 👣
Wusstest du...	dass zu viele Autofahrten zu Umweltverschmutzung, Verkehrschaos und Klimaerwärmung führen? 😞 Leiste deinen Beitrag und nutze die Öffis! 🚌
Wusstest du...	dass zu viele Autos die Stadt weniger lebenswert machen? 😞 Hilf mit, indem du mit dem Radl statt mit dem Auto fährst! 🚲
Wusstest du...	dass zu viele Autos die Stadt weniger lebenswert machen? 😞 Hilf mit, indem du zu Fuß gehst statt mit dem Auto zu fahren! 👣
Wusstest du...	dass zu viele Autos die Stadt weniger lebenswert machen? 😞 Hilf mit, indem du mit dem Radl fährst statt mit dem Auto! 🚲
Wusstest du...	dass viele Radler:innen sich grüßen, wenn sie gemeinsam im Regen radeln? 😞 Schnapp dein Rad und werde Teil dieser toughen Community! 🤝☁️
Warum fährst du nicht mit dem Rad?	Nach einer Radlfahrt wärst du heute sicher energiegeladen und entspannt! 🚲
Warum gehst du nicht zu Fuß zur Arbeit?	Nach einem Spaziergang wärst du sicher heute sicher energiegeladen und entspannt! 👣😊
Probier's das heute mal aus!	Radlfahren im Grünen ist schön und entspannend! 🚲🌳
Probier's das heute mal aus!	Ein Spaziergang im Grünen ist schön und entspannend! 👣🌳
Studien zeigen...	dass Leute, die zur Arbeit radeln, glücklicher sind! Warum versuchst du das heute nicht auch? 🚲😊
Studien zeigen...	dass Leute, die zu Fuß zur Arbeit gehen, glücklicher sind! Warum probierst du das heute nicht mal aus? 👣😊
Bist du diese Woche...	mit dem Radl gefahren? Was hat dir daran gefallen? 🚲😊
Bist du diese Woche...	zu Fuß zur Arbeit gegangen? Was hat dir daran gefallen? 👣😊
Da kannst du mithalten!	Die Science City radelt zur Arbeit - das kannst du auch! 🚲🤝

Wusstest du...	dass wir von der Science City es cool finden, mit dem Radl statt mit dem Auto in der Stadt unterwegs zu sein? 😊🚲
Wusstest du...	dass wir von der Science City es cool finden, zu Fuß statt mit dem Auto in der Stadt unterwegs zu sein? 😊👉
Deine Familie und Freunde...	sind sicher beeindruckt, wenn du häufig mit dem Radl statt mit dem Auto zur Arbeit fährst! 😊🚲
Deine Familie und Freunde...	sind sicher beeindruckt, wenn du zu Fuß in die Arbeit gehst statt mit dem Auto zu fahren! 👉😊
Da kannst du mithalten!	Wusstest du, dass viele Leute aus der Science City für den Arbeitsweg häufig die Öffis nutzen? 😞🚌
Wusstest du...	dass wir von der Science City es inspirierend finden, wenn Menschen die Öffis statt des Autos nutzen für den Arbeitsweg? 😊🚌
Da kannst du mithalten!	Deine Kolleg:innen sind häufig mit dem Radl unterwegs! Das schaffst du auch! 🚲👉
Deine Kolleg:innen hängen dich ab!	Zeit aufzuholen und heute mit dem Rad zu fahren! 🚲
Deine Kolleg:innen hängen dich ab!	Hast du auch geplant, heute mit dem Rad zu fahren? Mach doch mit! 🚲😊
Radlst du heute auch?	Viele deiner Kolleg:innen werden dem schlechten Wetter trotzen und zur Arbeit radeln - sei dabei! 🚲👉
Sei auch dabei!	Wusstest du, dass inzwischen viele Leute in der Science City zu Fuß gehen statt mit dem Auto zu fahren? 😞👉
Reminder...	Denk daran, heute mit dem Radl zu fahren! 🚲🎯
Reminder...	Denk daran, heute mit dem Radl zu fahren! Nichts kann dich aufhalten! 👉☁️
Reminder...	Warum radelst du nicht durch das Wochenende? 🚲😊
Wie wär's...	wenn du heute einen kleinen Spaziergang in deinen Arbeitsweg einplanst? Das Wetter ist wundervoll! 👉☀️
What a beautiful day! 🌻	Ein Spaziergang durch die Stadt ist eine hervorragende Aktivität fürs Wochenende! 👉😊
Reminder...	Morgen ist ein super Tag, um mit den Öffis zu fahren! 🚌
Reminder...	Am Wochenende mit den Öffis zu fahren ist "the way to go"! 🚌
Warum schnappst du dir...	nicht dein Lieblingsbuch und versuchst, diese Woche öfter mit Öffis zu fahren? 📖🚌
Du willst das Auto weniger nutzen?	Markier doch einen Tag in deinem Kalender, den du autofrei machst und stattdessen das Radl nutzt! 🎯🚲
Du willst das Auto weniger nutzen?	Markier doch einen Tag in deinem Kalender, den du autofrei machst und stattdessen zu Fuß gehst! 🎯👉
Du willst das Auto weniger nutzen?	Markier doch einen Tag in deinem Kalender, den du autofrei machst und stattdessen die Öffis nutzt! 🎯🚌
Was sind die Vor- und Nachteile...	das Radl im Alltag zu nutzen? Überleg mal, wie du die Nachteile zum Positiven ändern könntest! 😞🚲
Was sind die Vor- und Nachteile...	im Alltag zu Fuß zu gehen? Überleg mal, wie du die Nachteile zum Positiven ändern könntest! 😞👉
Was sind die Vor- und Nachteile...	im Alltag die Öffis zu nutzen? Überleg mal, wie du die Nachteile zum Positiven ändern könntest! 😞🚌
Du setzt deine Gesundheit aufs Spiel...	wenn du zu viel sitzt! Wie wär's heute mit einem Spaziergang zur Arbeit? 👉😊

Du setzt deine Gesundheit aufs Spiel...	wenn du zu viel sitzt! Wie wär's heute mit einer Radltour zur Arbeit? 🚲 😊
Gönn dir was! 📺	Warum planst du nicht eine kleine Belohnung ein, wenn du heute zur Arbeit radelst? Ein Eis, ein Stadtbummel... es kann alles sein!
Öffis können Spaß machen!	Hast du schlechte Erfahrungen mit den Öffis gemacht? Gib ihnen heute noch eine zweite Chance! 😞
Wie wär's...	wenn du gemütliche Schuhe für den Fußweg zur Arbeit trägst und ein schönes Paar im Büro lässt? Das macht den Weg viel angenehmer! 🧦 😊
Radlfahren ist zu anstrengend?	Pack dir Wechselkleidung ein falls du schwitzt oder leicht nass wirst, und sieh die Fahrt als dein Workout statt des Fitnessstudios! 😊 🏋️
Die Öffis brauchen ewig?	Nutz die Zeit für dich! Lies ein Buch, lern eine neue Sprache oder schau Katzenvideos an! 🐱
Heute schon an morgen denken	Ein bisschen Vorbereitung für deinen Radlweg zur Arbeit: Pack deine Sachen und leg sie an der Tür bereit z.B. Helm oder Rucksack!
Heute schon an morgen denken	Ein bisschen Vorbereitung für deinen Spaziergang zur Arbeit: Pack deine Taschen und such gute Musik aus!
Heute schon an morgen denken	Ein bisschen Vorbereitung für deine Öffifahrt zur Arbeit morgen? Pack deine Sachen und leg sie an der Tür bereit z.B. deine Tasche und ein Buch!
Gönn dir was! 📺	Ein cooles Gadget für dein Radl, ein bunter Helm, gemütlicher Rucksack oder passende Radlklamotten machen die Fahrt zur Arbeit deutlich spaßiger!
Gönn dir was! 📺	Gemütliche Schuhe für deinen Fußweg zur Arbeit macht deine Wege viel angenehmer und schöner!
Hilf mit! 🏋️	Du nutzt immer noch dein Auto für kurze Strecken? Warum steigst du als Klimaschützer:in nicht lieber aufs Radl um? 🚲
Hilf mit! 🏋️	Du nutzt immer noch dein Auto für kurze Strecken? Warum gehst du als Klimaschützer:in nicht lieber mehr zu Fuß? 🧦
Hilf mit! 🏋️	Du nutzt immer noch dein Auto für kurze Strecken? Warum steigst du als Klimaschützer:in nicht lieber auf die Öffis um? 🚊
Es dauert vielleicht länger...	mit dem Rad zur Arbeit zu fahren statt mit dem Auto - aber diese Zeit ist in deine Fitness und Gesundheit gut investiert! 🏋️ 🚲
Es dauert vielleicht länger...	zur Arbeit zu gehen statt mit dem Auto zu fahren - aber diese Zeit ist in deine Fitness und Gesundheit gut investiert! 🏋️ 🧦
Du schätzt Salzburg...	sicher sehr! Du persönlich kannst zur Nachhaltigkeit deiner Stadt beitragen, indem du radelst statt das Auto zu fahren! 🚲 😊
Du schätzt Salzburg...	sicher sehr! Du persönlich kannst zur Nachhaltigkeit deiner Stadt beitragen, indem du zu Fuß gehst statt das Auto zu fahren! 🧦 😊
Du schätzt Salzburg...	sicher sehr! Du persönlich kannst zur Nachhaltigkeit deiner Stadt beitragen, indem du die Öffis statt das Auto hernimmst! 🚊 😊
Die Öffis brauchen länger...	als dein Auto? Nutz die Zeit für dich selbst, lies ein Buch, lern eine neue Sprache oder arbeite ein paar Mails ab! 📖 🚊
Du kannst beitragen!	Du kannst zur Nachhaltigkeit in deiner Stadt beitragen! Wenn du zur Arbeit radelst, hast du deinen Teil geleistet! 🏋️ 🚲
Du kannst beitragen!	Du kannst zur Nachhaltigkeit in deiner Stadt beitragen! Wenn du zur Arbeit zu Fuß gehst, hast du deinen Teil geleistet! 🏋️ 🧦
Du kannst beitragen!	Du kannst zur Nachhaltigkeit in deiner Stadt beitragen! Wenn du die Öffis nimmst, hast du deinen Teil geleistet! 🏋️ 🚊
Fällt es dir schwer,	das Auto stehen zu lassen und das Radl zu nutzen? Denk an das letzte Mal, als das gut geklappt hat. Was hast du anders gemacht? 😞

Fällt es dir schwer,	das Auto stehen zu lassen und zu Fuß zu gehen? Denk an das letzte Mal, als das gut geklappt hat. Was hast du da anders gemacht? 😞
Fällt es dir schwer,	das Auto stehen zu lassen und mit den Öffis zu fahren? Denk an das letzte Mal, als das gut geklappt hat. Was hast du da anders gemacht? 😞
Stell dir vor...	du würdest mehr radeln - ob zur Arbeit oder am Wochenende! Du wärst fitter, energiegeladener und es hilft dir auch bei deiner Gesundheit! 😊
Stell dir vor...	du würdest mehr zu Fuß gehen - ob zur Arbeit oder am Wochenende! Du wärst fitter, energiegeladener und es hilft dir auch bei deiner Gesundheit! 😊